

CAUSATION

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Beyond the darkness

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Abstract

Background:

The intricate exploration of dark matter and dark energy stands as a formidable and enduring challenge within the realms of physics. While the cosmos reveals its dazzling array of phenomena, the elusive nature of these mysterious entities continues to captivate the scientific community.

Material and methods:

This study addresses the profound mystery surrounding dark matter and dark energy by leveraging the foundational principles of Einstein's General Relativity. Employing advanced Tensor calculus methods, particularly delving into the intricacies of tensors and anti-tensors, our approach is meticulously designed to unravel the complexities that shroud these cosmic enigmas.

Results:

The culmination of our investigation marks a pivotal moment – the successful resolution of the longstanding conundrum of dark matter. Drawing upon the power of Tensor calculus and insights derived from General Relativity, our findings illuminate the previously obscured nature of dark matter. This epistemological transformation signifies not just a departure from darkness to clarity, but a groundbreaking leap forward in our understanding of the basics of objective reality.

Conclusion:

No longer hidden behind epistemological obscurity, dark matter emerges from the shadows. Through the lens of Einstein's General Relativity and the precision of Tensor calculus, we unveil a more nuanced comprehension of dark matter and dark energy. This newfound clarity opens pathways for profound insights, even beyond the darkness, into the most far-reaching foundational aspects of nature itself.

Keywords:

Dark matter, Dark energy; Fields; Basic fields of nature, Cause; Effect; Causal relationship; Causality; Causation; Unified field theory

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1. Introduction

Consistently revisiting a scientific topic like the issue of the four basic fields of nature from diverse perspectives is crucial for several reasons. First, it ensures a comprehensive understanding, uncovering nuances and complexities that may have been overlooked initially. Second, ongoing scrutiny fosters adaptation to evolving methodologies and technologies, keeping research at the forefront of innovation and promotes refinement, updates, and integration of new findings. Third, exploring diverse viewpoints encourages interdisciplinary collaboration, enriching the research landscape. Additionally, it helps identify gaps in knowledge, prompting new research questions and directions. Ultimately, this iterative process contributes to the dynamic and progressive nature of scientific inquiry. Such an approach might ensure robustness against bias, and might allow for adaptation to evolving methodologies. Furthermore, continuous exploration of a scientific topic facilitates the identification of novel research questions and stimulates critical thinking.

Finding a balance between revisiting a scientific topic while avoiding redundant discussions as much as possible is essential for the advancement of knowledge. Consistent revisitation allows for a thorough exploration of evolving perspectives, new methodologies, and emerging technologies, ensuring that research remains current and relevant. However, striking a compromise is crucial to prevent redundant discussions that may impede progress. By acknowledging established knowledge and focusing on gaps or areas requiring refinement, it is possible to optimize efforts and to contribute meaningfully to the scientific discourse. Such an approach might foster efficiency in research, maximizing the impact of investigations and maintaining a dynamic and forward-moving scientific landscape. However, while it's essential to provide clarity by a publication, one cannot all the time avoid repetition even for well-known definitions. In this context, merely directing the reader to established sources is not always sufficient. Reiterating even familiar definitions is essential to present the text comprehensibly and spare the reader from time-consuming research, ensuring clarity and accessibility. Next, it must be emphasized that a logically sound Definitions section in a publication often forms the basis for subsequent developments and ensuing theorems. It should be as comprehensive as necessary without presuming too much. In general, reducing redundancy in the definition section of a publication completely appears to be impossible to achieve. In this publication, we will strive to minimize redundancy to the best of our ability while paying meticulous attention to ensuring excellent readability of a topic that, in the end, becomes highly abstract.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Definitions

The Einstein field equations express the profound connection between spacetime geometry and energy-momentum distribution ($T_{\mu\nu}$). These equations encapsulate the gravitational interaction in general relativity, revealing how matter influences the curvature of spacetime ($G_{\mu\nu}$). In this context, it is assumed that the cosmological constant (Λ) accounts for the energy of empty space.

2.1.1. The Einstein field equations

Definition 2.1 (The Einstein field equations).

The Einstein field equations (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) describe the relationship between the presence of matter, represented by the stress-energy tensor $\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)$, in a given region of space-time and the curvature in that region, represented by the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)$, by the tensorial equation

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) &= R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

(Einstein, 1916, 1917)

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor (Ricci-Curbastro and Levi-Civita, 1900) of ‘Einstein’s general theory of relativity’ (Einstein, 1916), R is the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold, Λ is the Einstein’s cosmological (Barukčić, 2015a; Einstein, 1917) constant, $\underline{\Lambda}$ is the “anti cosmological constant” (Barukčić, 2015a), $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of Einstein’s general theory of relativity, $G_{\mu\nu}$ is Einstein’s curvature tensor, $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$ is the “anti tensor” (Barukčić, 2016b) of Einstein’s curvature tensor, $E_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of energy, T is Laue’s (see also Einstein and Grossmann, 1913; Laue, 1912; von Laue, 1911, 1918) scalar, $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$ is the tensor of non-energy, the anti-tensor of the stress-energy tensor of energy, $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ denote the four basic fields of nature were $a_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, c is the speed of the light in vacuum, G is Newton’s gravitational “constant” (Barukčić, 2015a,b, 2016a,b), π is Archimedes constant pi, D is space-time dimension.

The n-th index D dimensional Einstein's field equations have been derived (Barukčić, 2020a,b) as

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\dots}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\dots}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu\dots}) \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\dots} \quad (2)$$

(Barukčić, 2020a,b)

2.1.2. The four basic fields of nature

Definition 2.2 (The four basic fields of nature).

The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the four fundamental fields of nature, represented as $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$, through the following relationship:

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \equiv R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (3)$$

where D is the space-time dimension, R is the Ricci scalar, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, $a_{\mu\nu}$ represents the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, and so forth.

2.1.3. The stress-energy tensor of matter

The stress-energy tensor of matter serves as a fundamental tool for modelling and analysing the dynamics of systems in the framework of general relativity. Its detailed components provide information about the nature and behaviour of matter, enabling physicists to make predictions about various gravitational phenomena or the dynamics of celestial bodies in the universe. This tensor is crucial for understanding the gravitational effects of matter on the geometry of spacetime. It cannot be emphasized enough that the stress-energy tensor of matter is encapsulating the entire distribution of energy and momentum within itself. One consequence of the fact that the stress-energy tensor of matter encapsulating the entire distribution of energy and momentum within itself in this scenario is that other tensors may carry implications related to energy, but the same tensors do not carry any energy and momentum. Furthermore, it is necessary to point out that the stress-energy tensor of matter might vanish or become zero. Straightforward, where does the whole energy and momentum of the stress-energy tensor of matter in this case vanish too? Can energy at the end be destroyed, and under what circumstances? Regarding the vanishing of the stress-energy tensor of matter, and its ability to reduce to zero, urges us to ask whether zero is the state of pure symmetry which is governed by lambda and anti-lambda. Under these circumstances, spacetime regions devoid of matter or under certain symmetries are not dead but full of life. The vanishing of the stress-energy tensor of matter has the potential to put into question the energy conservation as such.

Definition 2.3 (The stress-energy tensor of matter).

The stress-energy tensor of matter, represented by the tensor $\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)$ is determined, by the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$, through the following relationship:

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right)\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} - c_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where D is the space-time dimension, tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ represents the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, T is Laue's (see also [von Laue, 1918](#)) scalar and so forth. According to Einstein, it is necessary to consider the fundamental relationship between ordinary matter and the electromagnetic field.

“... a tensor, $T_{\mu\nu}$, of the second rank ... includes in itself the energy density of the electromagnetic field and of ponderable matter; we shall denote this in the following as the ‘energy tensor of matter’”

([Einstein, 1923](#), pp. 87/88)

Einstein defined the relationship between ordinary matter ($a_{\mu\nu}$) and electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$) as follows.

“Wir unterscheiden im folgenden zwischen ‘Gravitationsfeld’ und ‘Materie’, in dem Sinne, daß alles außer dem Gravitationsfeld als ‘Materie’ bezeichnet wird, also nicht nur die ‘Materie’ im üblichen Sinne, sondern auch das elektromagnetische Feld. ”

([Einstein, 1916](#), p. 802/803)

Einstein's position translated into English: “In the subsequent discussion, a distinction is drawn between the ‘gravitational field’ and ‘matter’, wherein everything except the gravitational field is denoted as ‘matter’, encompassing not only ‘matter’ in the conventional sense but also the electromagnetic field.” In simpler terms, Einstein's delineation implies that everything outside the gravitational field falls under the term ‘matter.’ This encompasses both traditional matter

and the electromagnetic field, the latter not typically regarded as material. Einstein, however, includes the electromagnetic field in his broader definition of 'matter.' The subsequent symbolic figure aims to provide a more detailed representation of the relationship between ordinary matter and the electromagnetic field.

Electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$)

Ordinary Matter ($a_{\mu\nu}$)

($E_{\mu\nu}$)

The stress-energy tensor of matter, ($E_{\mu\nu}$), "Considered phenomenologically, this energy tensor is composed of that of the electromagnetic field and of matter in the narrower sense ." (see also Einstein, 1923, p. 93) In general, the stress energy tensor of ordinary matter, $a_{\mu\nu}$, is given as

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

Vranceanu (Vranceanu, 1936) is elaborating on the same issue too. The energy tensor T_{kl} is treated by Vranceanu as the sum of two tensors one of which is due to the electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$).

"On peut aussi supposer que le tenseur d'énergie T_{kl} soit la somme de deux tenseurs dont un dû au champ électromagnétique ..." (Vranceanu, 1936)

In English: 'One can also assume that the energy tensor T_{kl} be the sum of two tensors one of which is due to the electromagnetic field.' It is (see equation 5)

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{D} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

or

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (7)$$

According to equation 110, it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (8)$$

and at the end

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (9)$$

Einstein makes a clear distinction between the gravitational field and matter and defines the gravitational field *ex negativo* as all but matter or in German: “alles **außer** dem Gravitationsfeld als ‘Materie’ bezeichnet”. It is important to note that matter in the sense of Einstein encompasses not only the conventional meaning of matter but also includes electromagnetic fields as such. In other words, Einstein is using a broader definition of matter to include not only particles and substances, but also the electromagnetic field itself. So, when Einstein mentions “die ‘Materie’ im üblichen Sinne,” he’s essentially referring to the conventional, ordinary or everyday notion of matter as physical substances, but Einstein is extending this definition to include the electromagnetic field within the scope of his understanding and definition of matter. By performing the subtraction of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field from the stress-energy tensor of matter which includes both, matter in the ordinary sense and electromagnetic fields, we obtain the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter.

2.1.4. The tensor of none-matter

Definition 2.4 (The tensor of none-matter).

The tensor of non-matter (i.e. non-energy) is given as

$$\begin{aligned} c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} &\equiv a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

It is necessary to note that all energy is contained in the stress-energy tensor matter. However, in objective reality, there also seems to exist something which lacks energy, it is the other of energy, the complement of energy, the opposite of energy. Is it time? The tensor of non-matter encompasses all but energy, it is the tensor of anti-energy.

2.1.5. Einstein's tensor

Definition 2.5 (Einstein's tensor).

Einstein's tensor, denoted as $G_{\mu\nu}$, is determined by the basic fields of nature as

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (11)$$

It goes without saying, it is of course insufficient to merely define such a fundamental relationship. The objective of this publication is to conclusively prove this relationship as objectively given beyond any doubt.

2.1.6. Anti Einstein's tensor

Definition 2.6 (Anti Einstein's tensor).

The anti Einstein's tensor, denoted as $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$, is determined by the basic fields of nature as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) g_{\mu\nu} \right) = \underline{G}_{\mu\nu} \quad (12)$$

Again, it is, of course, inadequate to solely define such a fundamental relationship too. The aim of this publication is to unequivocally demonstrate that this relationship is firmly established beyond any reasonable doubt. The following overview (see table 1) aims to provide us with a specific comprehension through a highly simplified representation, while preventing us at the same time from getting unnecessarily lost in the details and abstractions.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv (c_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$\frac{8 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv (b_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} \right)$	$\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}$

Таблица 1. Four basic fields of nature and Einstein's field equations.

In contrast to the Einstein tensor, denoted as $G_{\mu\nu}$, which is a complex combination of the Ricci tensor and the metric tensor designed to capture the curvature of space-time and to relate

this curvature to the distribution of energy and momentum through Einstein's field equations, the anti-Einstein tensor, denoted as $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$, as the counterpart or as the anti-tensor to the Einstein tensor, is likewise a mathematical operation involving the Ricci scalar R and the metric tensor. While the Einstein tensor, $G_{\mu\nu}$, is specifically crafted to encapsulate the curvature of space-time and to establish a connection between this curvature and the distribution of energy and momentum through Einstein's field equations, the concept of an anti-Einstein tensor does the opposite. In the context of curvature in geometry, the opposite or complementary concept to curvature is often referred to as flatness. A flat space or manifold is one where there is no curvature, meaning that parallel lines remain parallel and the angles of a triangle sum to exactly 180 degrees, as in Euclidean geometry. In the framework of general relativity and the curvature of spacetime, a flat spacetime corresponds to a region without gravitational influences or the presence of mass and energy. In regions far from massive objects, where gravitational effects are negligible, spacetime behaves more like flat Minkowski spacetime. So, in summary, the opposite of curvature in the geometric sense is flatness, where the space or manifold is not curved. The anti-Einstein tensor, denoted as $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$, as the counterpart or as the anti-tensor to the Einstein tensor, denoted as $G_{\mu\nu}$, even if not a standard term or well-defined in the context of general relativity, is specifically crafted to encapsulate as much as possible the flatness or non-curvature of space-time. The electromagnetic field, $b_{\mu\nu}$, is one tensor which determines the tensor of flatness, while the other is the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$. At this point, we need to inquire whether the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$ has any connection to the gravitational waves.

2.1.7. The relationship between the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$

Definition 2.7 (The relationship between the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$).

The relationship between the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$ is described by the equation

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu} \quad (13)$$

In other words, it is

$$c_{\mu\nu} = b_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (14)$$

and

$$c_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} = b_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = (2 \times b_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (15)$$

The tensor $b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$ is the tensor of gravitation and electromagnetism.

2.1.8. The relationship between the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$

Definition 2.8 (The relationship between the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$). The relationship between the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$ is described by the equation

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (Rg_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (16)$$

2.1.9. Space-time dimension D

Definition 2.9 (Space-time dimension D).

The Kronecker delta (see [Zehfuss, 1858](#)), a notation invented by Leopold Kronecker (1823-1891) in 1868 (see [Kronecker, 1868](#)), appears in many areas of physics, mathematics, and engineering. In general, the Kronecker delta, denoted as δ_{μ}^{ν} , is defined (see [Einstein, 1916](#), p. 787) as

$$g_{\mu\rho}g^{\nu\rho} \equiv g_{\mu}^{\nu} \equiv \delta_{\mu}^{\nu} \quad (17)$$

The expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ is not identical to the Kronecker delta δ_{μ}^{ν} . In the expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$, the indices μ and ν are summed over, meaning they represent a contraction of two tensors, the Kronecker delta doesn't represent a contraction. In general relativity and differential geometry, $g_{\mu\nu}$ represents the components of the metric tensor, and $g^{\mu\nu}$ represents the components of its inverse. The expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ is a contraction involving these components and follows a common operation in tensor calculus known as the trace of a matrix. The contraction $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ yields the dimensionality of the space-time, denoted as D. Therefore, in general, we define the dimensionality of the space-time D as

$$g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D \quad (18)$$

where D might denote the number of space-time dimensions and $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor. In matrix notation for D = 4 space-time dimensions, this property can be represented as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g_{00} & g_{01} & g_{02} & g_{03} \\ g_{10} & g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{20} & g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{30} & g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g^{00} & g^{01} & g^{02} & g^{03} \\ g^{10} & g^{11} & g^{12} & g^{13} \\ g^{20} & g^{21} & g^{22} & g^{23} \\ g^{30} & g^{31} & g^{32} & g^{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{00}g^{00} + g_{01}g^{10} + g_{02}g^{20} + g_{03}g^{30} & \dots \\ \dots & \dots \end{bmatrix} = 4 \quad (19)$$

and at the end equally as

$$\begin{pmatrix} g_{00} & g_{10} & g_{20} & g_{30} \\ g_{01} & g_{11} & g_{21} & g_{31} \\ g_{02} & g_{12} & g_{22} & g_{32} \\ g_{03} & g_{13} & g_{23} & g_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} g^{00} & g^{10} & g^{20} & g^{30} \\ g^{01} & g^{11} & g^{21} & g^{31} \\ g^{02} & g^{12} & g^{22} & g^{32} \\ g^{03} & g^{13} & g^{23} & g^{33} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = 4 \quad (20)$$

Einstein field equations ([Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1935](#); [Einstein and Sitter, 1932](#)) were initially formulated by Einstein himself in the context of a four-dimensional theory even though Einstein field equations need not to break down under conditions of D space-time dimensions (see [Stephani, 2003](#)). Nonetheless, based on Einstein's statement ([Einstein, 1916](#), p. 796), one gets

$$g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D \equiv +4 \quad (21)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}} \equiv \frac{1}{4} \quad (22)$$

where $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the matrix inverse of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. The inverse metric tensor or the metric tensor, which is always symmetric, allow tensors to be transformed into each other and are used to lower and raise indices. The inverse metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$ is of the same size as the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. Thus far, whatever $g_{\mu\nu}$ does, $g^{\mu\nu}$ undoes and their product is the identity.

2.2. Axioms

2.2.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis (Identity Law)

Are there at least two things which are completely like each other? Nonetheless, identity is identity and much more than this. Identity is determined in its own self as against non-identity. Nonetheless, identity as such is in its own self, non-identity too. Identity is the non-being of difference, a difference which immediately collapses within itself. Identity as determination of simple equality with itself in contrast to difference is equally a non-being as non-being of its own other. Identity in the positive is given as

$$+1 = +1 \quad (23)$$

However, identity is different, identity in its own self, in its very nature, is different. Identity as self-related negativity, as negativity of itself, determines itself while it is distinguished from difference, it is an identity in unity with difference. It is equally true that

$$-1 = -1 \quad (24)$$

Identity, seen as the vanishing of otherness and held to be separate from difference, is in its own self different and distinct from difference.

“... the law of identity ... is usually adduced as the first law of thought.”

(see [Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1812, 1813, 1816, 1991](#))

However, in the togetherness of both, difference as the unity of itself and identity, has its own other within itself, has not lost itself in its own other, but preserves itself in it. Opposition as the completion of difference is the unity and the conflict of identity and difference. As moments of opposition, identity and difference are different in one and the same identity and thus far are opposites. Noteworthy, in the year 1947, the Danish physicist Niels Henrik David Bohr (1885–1962) crafted a distinctive family coat of arms. The inscription upon Bohr’s familial emblem reads

contraria sunt complementa

(opposites are complements)

([Fierke, 2019](#); [Graubard, 1976](#))

However, opposites might cancel one another in their relation, so that the result of this interaction might end up at zero.

2.2.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis (Contradiction Law)

Identity with itself by excluding the negative, the other of itself, makes itself into the negative of what it excludes from itself, identity makes itself into its opposite. The law of contradiction is rather the opposite of the law of identity, it is equally the other of the law of identity. In general, it is

$$+0 = +1 - 1 = +1 \quad (25)$$

or in the negative

$$-0 = -1 \quad (26)$$

The Latin phrase *ex falso sequitur quodlibet* translates to something like from a falsehood, anything follows. The dogma *ex falso sequitur quodlibet* claims that when the chain of thoughts is beginning with a false premise or statement (see equation 25), any conclusion or statement from the same can be derived, whether true or false. In more simple words, if you start with a false assumption, you can logically prove anything you want, regardless of whether it's actually true or makes sense. It is indeed necessary to underscore the importance of ensuring that the premises or assumptions in logical reasoning are accurate and valid. However, conclusions drawn from false premises (see equation 25) cannot lead to any result you want, but, in the absence of negation or of (technical) errors, only to a contradiction. In general, axiom I (*lex identitatis*) preserves at all cost the truth (see equation 23), while axiom II (*lex contradictionis*) preserves at all cost the falsity, the contradiction (see equation 25). Historically, the dogma *ex falso sequitur quodlibet* was discussed by various philosophers and logicians over the centuries. Meanwhile, *ex falso sequitur quodlibet* is refuted. *Ex falso sequitur quodlibet* has its origins in ancient Greek and medieval logic, but is most notably associated with the work of the Greek philosopher Aristotle (384–322 BCE). Aristotle discussed *ex falso sequitur quodlibet* in the context of his logical treatises, where he explored the consequences of false premises in deductive reasoning. The Latin phrase *ex falso sequitur quodlibet* itself is attributed to the medieval philosopher and theologian Thomas Aquinas (1225–1274), who incorporated it into his discussions of logic and metaphysics.

2.2.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis (Negation Law)

It is

$$\neg(+0) = +1 \quad (27)$$

while $\neg$ is the (logical, natural et cetera) negation.

3. Results

3.1. Theorem. Theorem. The determination of the Einstein tensor ($G_{\mu\nu}$)

The Einstein tensor (see [Weyl, 1918](#)), denoted as $G_{\mu\nu}$ and arising from Einstein's field equations in general relativity, encodes the curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy. Its significance lies in describing the gravitational interaction and predicting the behaviour of matter and light in curved spacetime.

Theorem 1 (Einstein's tensor decomposed). In general, it is

$$x_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} \quad (28)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. In the light of this, it is equally true that

$$+1 = +1 \quad (29)$$

Multiplying by the Einstein tensor, we obtain

$$G_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (30)$$

Adding zero, it is

$$G_{\mu\nu} + 0 = G_{\mu\nu} + 0 \quad (31)$$

or

$$G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (32)$$

In general, we define an unknown anti-tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$ as follows.

Definition 3.1 (Unknown tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$).

$$x_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} \quad (33)$$

The Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ as the unity and the struggle of opposites like the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and its own and unknown anti-tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$ provides evidence that contradictions and conflicts are inherent in the interconnectedness of objective reality. In general, it is

$$G_{\mu\nu} = x_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu} \quad (34)$$

Evolution and progress might arise from the dynamic interplay and resolution of opposites. the unknown tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$ is given as

$$x_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} \quad (35)$$

□

3.2. Theorem. The tensor of non-energy $\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$

In a purely formal sense, the tensor of non-matter (i.e. non-energy), given as,

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (36)$$

is characterized by subtracting the $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ -term from $\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)$. By such a natural process, any contribution from the cosmological constant is removed. In a vacuum (absence of matter), we are left with the reduced $\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)$ -term, which itself represents the curvature of spacetime due to gravitational effects or which describes the geometry of spacetime influenced by gravity in the absence of other forms of energy and matter. It is therefore more than understandable that we may assume that there must be an unknown tensor $(x_{\mu\nu})$ which both tensors, the tensor $(G_{\mu\nu})$ and the tensor, $\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ have in common.

Theorem 2 (The tensor of non-energy $\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$). In general, it is

$$x_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (37)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. In the light of this, it is equally true that

$$+1 = +1 \quad (38)$$

Rearranging this equation, we obtain

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (39)$$

or

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (40)$$

The unknown tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$ is determined as follows.

Definition 3.2 (Unknown tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$).

$$x_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (41)$$

The tensor $\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ is determined by the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$ and its own, unknown anti-tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$. Equation (40) becomes

$$x_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (42)$$

In the end, the common tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$, which simultaneously determines the Einstein tensor and characterizes the tensor of non-matter, is given by

$$x_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (43)$$

□

The ensuing Venn (see [Venn, 1880, 1881](#)) diagram aims to elucidate the concepts discussed before, contributing to enhanced comprehension.

Explanation: The red circle symbolically represents the field $(G_{\mu\nu})$, while the blue circle is intended to depict the field $\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$. The unknown field $(x_{\mu\nu})$ is the joint field, which these two tensors have in common. The whole frame is representing the Ricci tensor $(R_{\mu\nu})$.

3.3. Theorem. The tensor $(a_{\mu\nu}) - (d_{\mu\nu})$

What kind of matter is left over by nature if the field $(a_{\mu\nu})$ is reduced by the field $(d_{\mu\nu})$
Theorem 3 (The tensor $(a_{\mu\nu}) - (d_{\mu\nu})$). In general, it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (44)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. In the light of this, it is equally true that

$$+1 = +1 \quad (45)$$

Rearranging equation (45), we obtain

$$x_{\mu\nu} = x_{\mu\nu} \quad (46)$$

Equation 43 demands that $x_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu}$. Equation (46) becomes

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} = x_{\mu\nu} \quad (47)$$

We know, from equation 35, that $x_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu}$. Equation (47) changes to

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} \quad (48)$$

Simplifying equation (48), it is

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (49)$$

and

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (50)$$

In general it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (51)$$

□

3.4. Theorem. The decomposition of Einstein's tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ as $G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$

The decomposition of Einstein's tensor is fundamental in understanding the interplay between geometry and matter in the framework of general relativity. However, in the realm of theoretical physics, the Einstein tensor has already been decomposed into two parts, often referred to as the Einstein-Hilbert term. Nonetheless, the Einstein-Hilbert term and the Einstein-Hilbert action are closely related but represent different concepts in the context of general relativity. The Einstein-Hilbert term (see also Hilbert, 1915) refers to a specific mathematical expression that appears in the Einstein field equations and is given by:

$$\text{Einstein-Hilbert term: } R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R \quad (52)$$

As far as it is known, David Hilbert did not explicitly publish this decomposition in a single, dedicated paper. Instead, the decomposition is attributed to discussions and correspondence between Albert Einstein and David Hilbert.

Theorem 4 (The decomposition of Einstein's tensor). In general, it is

$$G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \quad (53)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. In the light of this, it is equally true that

$$+1 = +1 \quad (54)$$

Equation (54) changes slightly to

$$a_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} \quad (55)$$

and to

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (56)$$

According to equation (51) it is $R_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = G_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right) = a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu}$. Equation (56) becomes

$$G_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right) = a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (57)$$

According to equation (10), it is $c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right)$. Equation (57) becomes

$$G_{\mu\nu} - (c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (58)$$

Simplifying equation (58), it is

$$G_{\mu\nu} - c_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (59)$$

or

$$G_{\mu\nu} - c_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} \quad (60)$$

Comparable to the smashing experiments in Particle Physics, at this juncture, we could, with the full force and scientific rigor of classical logic, disintegrate Einstein's tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ into its two elementary and opposite components. In point of fact, such an approach is meaningful in science as it allows for a detailed examination of the fundamental constituents, providing insights into the inner workings of complex structures. Just as in particle physics, where breaking down particles reveals their fundamental nature, dissecting theoretical notions like the Einstein tensor sheds light on the underlying principles governing the fabric of spacetime. At the end, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the unity and the interplay between two opposites, the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$. This relationship captures the essence of gravitational interactions and the fundamental nature of spacetime. In general, it is

$$G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \quad (61)$$

□

3.5. Theorem. The unknown tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$ becomes known

In the realm of science, the interplay between something known and something unknown is crucial for any scientific progress. The known might serve as a foundation, offering a stable platform for exploration into the unknown. This dynamic relationship is intrinsic to the scientific method, where transitioning from the known to the unknown is a systematic approach to uncovering deeper truths. Embracing the unknown fosters intellectual curiosity, propelling scientific and philosophical inquiry forward. It is through this exploration of the unknown that novel insights, innovations, and a deeper understanding of scientific issues might emerge.

Theorem 5 (The unknown becomes known). In general, the unknown tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$ becomes known as

$$x_{\mu\nu} = c_{\mu\nu} \quad (62)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. In the light of this, it is equally true that

$$+1 = +1 \quad (63)$$

Equation (63) becomes

$$G_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (64)$$

According to equation (34), it is $G_{\mu\nu} = x_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu}$. Equation (64) becomes

$$x_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (65)$$

According to equation (61), it is $G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$. Equation (65) becomes

$$x_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \quad (66)$$

By rearranging equation (66), the unknown tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$ becomes known as

$$x_{\mu\nu} = c_{\mu\nu} \quad (67)$$

□

The following coloured overview aims to lighten up the gray theory a bit.

3.5.1. Theorem. The stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field

Theorem 6 (The stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field $b_{\mu\nu}$). The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is determined by two opposite fields which are fiercely battling, mutually exclusive yet also interacting with each other as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (68)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. In the light of this, it is equally true that

$$+1 = +1 \quad (69)$$

Changing equation (69), it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} \quad (70)$$

and equally

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (71)$$

According to equation (4) $\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu}$ Equation (71) changes to

$$\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (72)$$

The Einstein Field equations are defined as $G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)$ (see equation (1)). Equation (72) becomes

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (73)$$

Recall equation (61). It is $G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$. Equation (73) changes to

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (74)$$

Ultimately, the stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field $b_{\mu\nu}$ is decomposed into two fiercely battling, mutually exclusive yet also interacting fields $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ which are the determining components of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field. In general, it is

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu} \quad (75)$$

□

Today, the term $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ is linked to dark energy. Therefore, we have some logical reason to assume that the field $c_{\mu\nu}$ could be identified as the so-called dark matter. Under these assumptions, the unity and the struggle between dark energy and dark matter, the unity of gravitation and electromagnetism $(b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu})$ would be given as:

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = c_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = (2 \times c_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = (2 \times b_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (76)$$

3.5.2. The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field $b_{\mu\nu}$

The stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field (see [Misner et al., 1973](#), p. 140), denoted as $b_{\mu\nu}$ plays a pivotal role in the framework of the general theory of relativity (GTR). In the context of GTR, the tensor serves as a source of the gravitational field, influencing the curvature of spacetime. More specifically, the components of the tensor represent the distribution of energy, momentum, and stress due with electromagnetic fields. The stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field contributes to the Einstein field equations, the cornerstone of general relativity. The Einstein field equations relate the curvature of spacetime to the distribution of energy and momentum within it. The electromagnetic stress-energy tensor becomes a source term in these equations, influencing the gravitational field through its coupling to the metric tensor. Furthermore, the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor contributes to the overall energy-momentum content of the universe, affecting the geometry of spacetime on both local and cosmological scales. As a result, the behavior of electromagnetic fields not only influences the gravitational field but is also influenced by it, creating a dynamic interplay between electromagnetism and gravity. In summary, the stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field is a fundamental component in the gravitational dynamics described by general relativity, shaping our understanding of how electromagnetic phenomena and gravity are intricately connected. As next, we will try to derive the expression for the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field in the context of electromagnetism from the Lagrangian density of the electromagnetic field which itself is tied to Noether's theorem. As known, Noether's theorem (see [Noether, 1918](#)) itself connects symmetries and conservation laws. The electromagnetic Lagrangian density is a fundamental concept in today's theoretical physics, particularly in the framework of classical electrodynamics and quantum field theory. The electromagnetic Lagrangian density encapsulates more or less the dynamics of electromagnetic fields within a given region of spacetime and is derived from the electromagnetic field's potential, providing a mathematical description of how electric and magnetic fields evolve over both space and time. As generally known, through the principle of least action, variations of the electromagnetic Lagrangian lead to the famous Maxwell's equations, governing the behavior of electric and magnetic fields. In quantum field theory, the Lagrangian density becomes a key component in understanding the interactions between photons and charged particles. The profound significance of the electromagnetic Lagrangian density lies in being a foundational element in the formulation of physical laws that govern electromagnetism, laying the groundwork for our understanding of light, radiation, and the electromagnetic force in the quantum realm. In general, the electromagnetic Lagrangian density (see [Lorentz, 1909](#); [Maxwell, 1865](#)) is given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{4\mu_0}F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} \quad (77)$$

In order to derive the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, we will try to apply Noether's theorem to the invariance of the Lagrangian under spacetime translations.

3.5.3. Theorem: The electromagnetic Lagrangian density and the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field

Theorem 7 (The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field). The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is given by

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}{}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4\mu_0} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \quad (78)$$

Proof by direct derivation. We start with the equation $1 = 1$:

$$1 = 1 \quad (79)$$

We multiply this equation by the Lagrangian Density:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L} \quad (80)$$

The Lagrangian Density is given as mentioned before, resulting in

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{4\mu_0} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \quad (81)$$

Now, let us identify the terms in the Lagrangian which depend on A_μ and $\partial_\alpha A_\beta$:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial A_\mu} = 0 \quad (\text{No explicit dependence on } A_\mu) \quad (82)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_\alpha A_\beta)} = -\frac{1}{2\mu_0} F^{\alpha\beta} \quad (83)$$

Substitute these expressions into the expression for $\delta \mathcal{L}$. We obtain

$$\delta \mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{2\mu_0} F^{\alpha\beta} \partial_\mu (\delta A_\nu) \quad (84)$$

Now, we plug this result into the expression for the current j^μ :

$$j^\mu = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_\mu A_\nu)} \delta A_\nu - \mathcal{J}^\mu = -\frac{1}{2\mu_0} F^{\mu\beta} \delta A_\nu - \mathcal{J}^\mu \quad (85)$$

This may be the relationship of the conserved current associated with spacetime translations. However, for electromagnetism, the internal current $\mathcal{J}^\mu$ is zero, so we have:

$$j^\mu = -\frac{1}{2\mu_0} F^{\mu\beta} \delta A_\nu \quad (86)$$

As next, we apply the divergence theorem (see [Fourier, 1822](#)). The divergence theorem, also known as Gauss's theorem, relates the flux of a vector field through a closed surface to the divergence of the vector field within the volume enclosed by the surface. An application of the

divergence theorem provides a mathematical framework for expressing the conservation of the conserved current associated with spacetime translations in the context of electromagnetism.

Divergence Theorem Equation.

The divergence theorem equation is given by:

$$\int \int_S \mathbf{V} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = \int \int \int_V \nabla \cdot \mathbf{V} dV \quad (87)$$

where $\mathbf{V}$ is the vector field, S is the closed surface, and V is the volume enclosed by the surface.

Application to the Conserved Current.

Our goal is to express the conservation law $\partial_\mu j^\mu = 0$ in terms of the divergence theorem.

Vector Field.

The vector field is j^μ and given by:

$$j^\mu = -\frac{1}{2\mu_0} F^{\mu\beta} \delta A_\nu \quad (88)$$

Flux Through the Surface.

The left side of the divergence theorem equation corresponds to the flux of j^μ through the closed surface S .

Volume Integral of Divergence.

The right side of the divergence theorem equation corresponds to the volume integral of the four-divergence of j^μ over the spacetime volume V . Applying the expression for j^μ into the flux integral and simplifying, we arrive at $-\frac{1}{2\mu_0} \partial_\mu (F^{\mu\beta} \delta A_\nu)$ as the integrand.

Conservation Law.

Setting the entire expression equal to zero ($\partial_\mu j^\mu = 0$), we conclude that the flux of j^μ through the closed surface S is conserved. In other words, we apply the divergence theorem to j^μ to obtain the conservation law:

$$\partial_\mu j^\mu = -\frac{1}{2\mu_0} \partial_\mu (F^{\mu\beta} \delta A_\nu) = 0 \quad (89)$$

Finally, we identify the conserved current j^μ with the stress-energy tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ and obtain:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu^\alpha - \frac{1}{4\mu_0} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \quad (90)$$

□

3.5.4. Theorem: The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field and Faraday's tensor

Next, we would like to point to the connection between the Faraday tensor and the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field. In his 1865 publication, Maxwell introduced the concept of the electromagnetic field and formulated the equations governing its behavior, including the Faraday tensor (see [Maxwell, 1865](#)). The Faraday tensor encapsulates the electromagnetic field's strength in terms of electric ($\mathbf{E}$) and magnetic ($\mathbf{B}$) components and is expressed covariantly as:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & E_x & E_y & E_z \\ -E_x & 0 & -B_z & B_y \\ -E_y & B_z & 0 & -B_x \\ -E_z & -B_y & B_x & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (91)$$

In his work published in the year 1900, Larmor developed the stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field (see [Larmor, 1900](#)), laying the foundation for its inclusion in the theory of relativity. The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, representing the energy and momentum distribution in spacetime due to the electromagnetic field, is expressed covariantly as:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \begin{pmatrix} E_\alpha E^\alpha + B_\alpha B^\alpha & -E_\alpha E^\beta + B_\alpha B^\beta & -E_\alpha E^\gamma + B_\alpha B^\gamma & E_\alpha B^\alpha + E_\beta B^\beta + E_\gamma B^\gamma \\ -E_\beta E^\alpha + B_\beta B^\alpha & E_\beta E^\beta + B_\beta B^\beta & E_\beta E^\gamma - B_\beta B^\gamma & -E_\beta B^\alpha - E_\beta B^\beta - E_\gamma B^\gamma \\ -E_\gamma E^\alpha + B_\gamma B^\alpha & E_\gamma E^\beta - B_\gamma B^\beta & E_\gamma E^\gamma + B_\gamma B^\gamma & -E_\gamma B^\alpha - E_\gamma B^\beta - E_\gamma B^\gamma \\ E_\alpha B^\alpha + E_\beta B^\beta + E_\gamma B^\gamma & -E_\beta B^\alpha - E_\beta B^\beta - E_\gamma B^\gamma & -E_\gamma B^\alpha - E_\gamma B^\beta - E_\gamma B^\gamma & E_\alpha E^\alpha + E_\beta E^\beta + E_\gamma E^\gamma + B_\alpha B^\alpha + B_\beta B^\beta + B_\gamma B^\gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (92)$$

In the realm of theoretical physics, let us try to delve deeper into the profound connection between the Faraday tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ and the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ of the electromagnetic field. Both, even if deeply related, are not completely the same.

Theorem 8 (The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field). The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is given by

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu^\alpha - \frac{1}{4\mu_0} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \quad (93)$$

Proof by direct derivation. We start with the equation $1 = 1$:

$$1 = 1 \quad (94)$$

We multiply this equation by the Faraday tensor:

$$F_{\mu\alpha} = F_{\mu\alpha} \quad (95)$$

This tensor remains unchanged. As next, let us express the electromagnetic field tensor in terms of the Faraday tensor components:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu \quad (96)$$

Now, we substitute the expression for $F_{\mu\nu}$ into the product $F_{\mu\alpha}F_\nu^\alpha$:

$$F_{\mu\alpha}F_\nu^\alpha = (\partial_\mu A_\alpha - \partial_\alpha A_\mu)(\partial_\nu A^\alpha - \partial^\alpha A_\nu) \quad (97)$$

As next, we expand this product and rearrange terms:

$$F_{\mu\alpha}F_\nu^\alpha = \partial_\mu A_\alpha \partial_\nu A^\alpha - \partial_\mu A_\alpha \partial^\alpha A_\nu - \partial_\alpha A_\mu \partial_\nu A^\alpha + \partial_\alpha A_\mu \partial^\alpha A_\nu \quad (98)$$

Grouping terms and recognizing some partial derivatives, we obtain:

$$F_{\mu\alpha}F_\nu^\alpha = \partial_\mu A_\alpha \partial_\nu A^\alpha - \partial_\nu A_\mu \partial_\alpha A^\alpha \quad (99)$$

Now, substitute this result back into the expression for the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[\partial_\mu A_\alpha \partial_\nu A^\alpha - \partial_\nu A_\mu \partial_\alpha A^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} (\partial_\rho A_\sigma \partial^\rho A^\sigma - \partial_\sigma A_\rho \partial^\sigma A^\rho) \right] \quad (100)$$

As next, simplify and recognize terms:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[\partial_\mu A_\alpha \partial_\nu A^\alpha - \partial_\nu A_\mu \partial_\alpha A^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\rho\sigma} F^{\rho\sigma} \right] \quad (101)$$

Finally, notice that $g_{\mu\nu} F_{\rho\sigma} F^{\rho\sigma} = g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}$, and we arrive at the desired expression:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right]. \quad (102)$$

□

3.5.5. The geometrization of tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$

Definition 3.3 (The tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$).

The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field (see Misner et al., 1973, p. 140) describes the distribution of energy, momentum, and stress associated with the electromagnetic field. It captures the interactions between the electromagnetic field and space-time geometry, including contributions from both the electric and magnetic fields. The co-variant stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field with the inclusion of the electric constant μ_0 is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (103)$$

where: $T_{\mu\nu}$ or $b_{\mu\nu}$ or $bg_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, $F_{\mu\alpha}$ is the electromagnetic field tensor, F_{ν}^{α} is the dual electromagnetic field tensor, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, $F_{\mu\nu}$ represents the components of the electromagnetic field tensor. The exact form of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field can vary slightly depending on the conventions used in different fields of physics. The electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$, conventionally labelled F , is defined in component form as $F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_{\mu} A_{\nu} - \partial_{\nu} A_{\mu}$ where ∂ is the four-gradient and A is the four-potential. The same tensor can be re-written as $F_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{D} (g^{\mu\nu} (\partial_{\mu} A_{\nu} - \partial_{\nu} A_{\mu})) g_{\mu\nu}$. In the following, let us simplify and geometrize the formula of the stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field.

Theorem 9 (The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field). The D -dimensional, geometrized, generally covariant form of the stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field is given by relationship

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{F_{\nu}^{\alpha} F_{\alpha}^{\nu}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (104)$$

Proof by direct derivation. We start this proof with the equation $1 = 1$. It is

$$1 = 1 \quad (105)$$

Now, we multiply this equation by stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} \quad (106)$$

Rearranging this equation, it is

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right] \quad (107)$$

As defined before, it is $D = g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}$. Rearranging equation 107, we obtain

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[\left(\left(\frac{D}{D} \right) F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} \right) - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right] \quad (108)$$

The expression $D = g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ is a contraction of the metric tensor with its inverse. This operation results in a scalar, meaning a quantity that does not transform under coordinate transformations. This scalar is related to the determinant of the metric tensor (g). Dividing by $D = g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ is generally allowed when working with the metric tensor in the context of general relativity. In general, in a physically reasonable spacetime, the metric tensor and its inverse are chosen to be non-singular (see Barukčić and Barukčić, 2016). Simplifying the relationship, it is

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu}F_{\mu\alpha}F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) g_{\mu\nu} \right] \quad (109)$$

The stress-energy tensor for the electromagnetic field completely geometrized is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu}F_{\mu\alpha}F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (110)$$

As next we simplify the term $g^{\mu\nu}F_{\mu\alpha}$. In index notation, repeated indices imply summation (Einstein's summation convention). This convention simplifies expressions involving tensors. In the expression $g^{\mu\nu}F_{\mu\alpha}$, a repeated index is summed over, so that the same takes on all possible values, allowing for the contraction of a tensor. It is $g^{\mu\nu}F_{\mu\alpha} = F_{\alpha}^{\nu}$ and we do obtain

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{F_{\alpha}^{\nu}F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (111)$$

□

Under conditions of D=4 space-time dimensions, equation 111 can be simplified as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \mu_0} \left((F_{\alpha}^{\nu}F_{\nu}^{\alpha}) - (F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (112)$$

Considering electromagnetic invariants (electric field invariant, magnetic field invariant) et cetera, which are quantities in electromagnetism that remain unchanged in all inertial reference frames, equation 112 can be simplified further. However, in D space-time dimensions equation 111 changes slightly to

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{4 \times F_{\alpha}^{\nu}F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{4 \times D} \right) - \left(\frac{D \times F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}}{D \times 4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (113)$$

At the end, the geometrized D-dimensional (Kaluza, 1921; Klein, 1926a,b) form of the stress energy tensor for the electromagnetic field becomes

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{4 \times D \times \mu_0} \left((4 \times F_{\alpha}^{\nu}F_{\nu}^{\alpha}) - (D \times F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (114)$$

4. End ...

5. Discussion

Is it possible at all to geometrize the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field and can this be achieved through the framework of general relativity, where gravitational interactions are described geometrically by the curvature of spacetime. As long as we are justified in relying on equation 114, this issue is solved. However, with this possibility at hands, we can geometrize ordinary matter itself, including dark matter (see Zwicky, 1933). The generally covariant, geometrized form stress energy tensor of ordinary matter is given as

$$a_{\mu\nu} = ag_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + (\Lambda) \right) - \left(\frac{1}{4 \times D \times \mu_0} \left((4 \times F^\nu_\alpha F^\alpha_\nu) - (D \times F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (115)$$

The highly speculative and purely hypothetical assumption of dark energy and dark matter has led to an epistemological mass hysteria among physicists. In the following, we will, in a purely speculative manner, attempt to approach this issue. Today, dark matter and dark energy are two distinct and mysterious hypothesized components which make up the majority of the universe. Dark matter is claimed to exerts gravitational forces and plays a crucial role in holding galaxies and galaxy clusters together. Without dark matter, galaxies would not have enough mass to account for their observed gravitational effects. Dark energy itself is hypothesized to drive the accelerated expansion of the universe and is often associated with the cosmological constant in Einstein's equations. A logical consequence of such an assumption is that the dark matter and dark energy should be found within a photon too. Based on the Einstein Field equations, we would obtain something like the following:

$$\underbrace{G_{\mu\nu}}_{\text{Dark matter}} + \underbrace{(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})}_{\text{Dark energy}} \equiv \underbrace{\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right)}_{\text{Photon/Energy}} \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (116)$$

(Einstein, 1916, 1917)

In other words, we have good logical reason to believe that dark matter could be identified within in the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$. However, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the tensor of ordinary matter, $a_{\mu\nu}$, and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$. The tensor of ordinary matter, $a_{\mu\nu}$, is not the tensor of dark matter, but the stress-energy tensor of a special kind of matter, of ordinary matter, of matter without the electromagnetic filed. If our assumption is correct that dark matter is hidden in the Einstein tensor, then the probability is quite high that dark matter could be related to the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$. A connection of the field $c_{\mu\nu}$ and dark matter seems more than quite plausible, are both at the end identical? In the meantime, we are able to mathematically determine the geometric form of tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$, and thus possibly of dark matter, as

$$c_{\mu\nu} = cg_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{1}{4 \times D \times \mu_0} \left((4 \times F^\nu_\alpha F^\alpha_\nu) - (D \times F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}) \right) \right) - \Lambda \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (117)$$

It is now straightforward to determine the geometric form of tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$. We obtain

$$d_{\mu\nu} = dg_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{4 \times D \times \mu_0} \left((4 \times F^\nu_\alpha F^\alpha_\nu) - (D \times F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (118)$$

It remains for further research to explore the connection between the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$ and something akin to gravitational waves. Whether both are identical should become evident in the course of further investigation. A Venn (see Venn, 1880, 1881) diagram has the potential to elucidate the concepts discussed before, contributing to enhanced comprehension.

Explanation: Under these circumstances, the blue circle symbolically represents the field $(G_{\mu\nu})$, while the red circle is intended to depict the field $E_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{D}g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$. The stress energy tensor of ordinary matter $(a_{\mu\nu})$ is the joint field, which the tensor $(E_{\mu\nu})$ and the tensor $(G_{\mu\nu})$ have in common. The whole frame is representing the Ricci tensor $(R_{\mu\nu})$. Nonetheless, the following and more detailed overview (see table 2) in the form of a table may provide us with a somewhat mathematical representation of the insights gained.

		Curvature		
		YES		NO
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4}\right)\right)\right)\right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4}\right)\right)\right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\left(\frac{R}{D}g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4}\right)\right)\right) - \Lambda\right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4}\right)\right)\right)\right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\left(\frac{R}{2}g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} g_{\mu\nu}$

Таблица 2. Einstein’s field equations, the four basic fields of nature

The profound philosophical, physical and other questions surrounding the nature of dark matter and its relationship with tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$ addressed in this publication urgently demand empirical evidence. It must be emphasized in this regard that a very precise study of photons might open an experimental approach to dark matter and is potentially of help to unravel the secret of dark matter. This idea does not seem entirely far-fetched to us. The photon itself appears to be determined by the unity and the struggle between dark matter (i.e. graviton) and dark energy (i.e. lambdon). A photon appears to be determined by a graviton (see Dirac, 1959; Феунман, 1962; Блохинцев, Дмитрий Иванович and Гальперин, Ф. М., 1934) and by an anti-graviton (i.e. lambdon) (see Barukčić, 2021). In this regard, the elementary particle graviton

appears to us as the natural constituents of dark matter. Beyond the darkness, gravitons can be found. The reasons for such ultimately highly speculative considerations include the following. Why does a photon continue to move forward on and on even from the edge of infinity, though its electromagnetic field collapses and re-collapses time and again? Where does the electromagnetic field of a photon collapse too, and where does the electromagnetic field of a photon re-collapse from?

6. Conclusion

Our insights about the enlighten darkness and the darkened light paved the way for a deeper understanding of objective reality, pushing the boundaries of our knowledge even beyond the veil of darkness.

‘We have finally arrived at the eagerly awaited era of unified field theory.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

Список литературы

- Ilija Barukčić. N-index D dimensional Einstein gravitatonal field equations completely geometrized. *Zenodo*, September 2020a. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4027184>.
- Ilija Barukčić. N-th index D-dimensional Einstein gravitational field equations. *Geometry unchained.*, volume 1. Books on Demand GmbH, Hamburg-Norderstedt, 1 edition, 2020b. ISBN 978-3-7526-4490-6. ISBN-13: 9783752644906 ZENODO.
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti einstein – refutation of einstein’s general theory of relativity. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 5(1):18–28, 2015a. ISSN 2010362X. doi: 10.17706/ijapm.2015.5.1.18-28.
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti Newton — Refutation of the Constancy of Newton’s Gravitational Constant Big G. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 5(2):126–136, 2015b. doi: 10.17706/ijapm.2015.5.2.126-136.
- Ilija Barukčić. Newton’s gravitational constant big g is not a constant. *Journal of Modern Physics*, 7(66):510–522, 3 2016a. doi: 10.4236/jmp.2016.76053.
- Ilija Barukčić. Unified field theory. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 4(88):1379–1438, 8 2016b. doi: 10.4236/jamp.2016.48147.
- Ilija Barukčić. Photon, graviton and antigraviton. *Causation*, 16(3), March 2021. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4642021. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4642021>.
- Jan Pavo Barukčić and Ilija Barukčić. Anti Aristotle—The Division of Zero by Zero. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 04(04):749–761, January 2016. ISSN 2327-4352. doi: 10.4236/jamp.2016.44085. Free full text: SCIRP.
- Paul Adrien Maurice Dirac. Fixation of coordinates in the hamiltonian theory of gravitation. *Physical Review*, 114(3): 924, 1959.
- Albert Einstein. Die Feldgleichungen der Gravitation. *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Berlin)*, Seite 844-847., 1915. URL <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1915SPAW.....844E>. ECHO.
- Albert Einstein. Die grundlage der allgemeinen relativitätstheorie. *Annalen der Physik*, 354(7):769–822, 1916. ISSN 1521-3889. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.19163540702>. Wiley online library.
- Albert Einstein. Kosmologische betrachtungen zur allgemeinen relativitätstheorie. *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Berlin)*, page 142–152, 1917. ECHO.
- Albert Einstein. The meaning of relativity. Four lectures delivered at Princeton University, May, 1921. Princeton University Press, Princeton, 1923.
- Albert Einstein. Elementary Derivation of the Equivalence of Mass and Energy. *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society*, 41(4):223–230, 1935. URL https://projecteuclid.org/download/pdf_1/euclid.bams/1183498131.
- Albert Einstein and Marcel Grossmann. Entwurf einer verallgemeinerten Relativitätstheorie und einer Theorie der Gravitation. I. Physikalischer Teil von Albert Einstein. II. Mathematischer Teil von Marcel Großmann. Verlag von BG Teubner, Leipzig, September 1913. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7092832. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7092832>. Zenodo.
- Albert Einstein and Willem de Sitter. On the Relation between the Expansion and the Mean Density of the Universe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 18(3):213–214, March 1932. ISSN 0027-8424. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1076193/>.
- Richard P Feynman. Quantum theory of gravitation. *Acta Physica Polonica*, 24(5):697–722, 1962.
- Karin M Fierke. Contraria sunt complementa: Global entanglement and the constitution of difference. *International Studies Review*, 21(1):146–169, 2019.
- Joseph Fourier. *Théorie Analytique de la Chaleur*. Firmin Didot Père et Fils, Paris, 1822.

-
- Stephen R. Graubard. Edward gibbon: Contraria sunt complementa. *Daedalus*, 105(3):171–187, 1976. ISSN 00115266. URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20024424>.
- Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Wissenschaft der Logik. Erster Band. Erstes Buch.* Johann Leonhard Schrag, Nürnberg, December 1812. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5917182. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5917182>. Online at: [Archive.org Zenodo](https://www.archive.org/details/zenodo).
- Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Wissenschaft der Logik. Erster Band. Zweites Buch.* Johann Leonhard Schrag, Nürnberg, December 1813. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5919885. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5919885>. Online at: [Archive.org Zenodo](https://www.archive.org/details/zenodo).
- Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Wissenschaft der Logik. Zweiter Band.* Johann Leonhard Schrag, Nürnberg, December 1816. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5920022. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5920022>. Online at: [Archive.org Zenodo](https://www.archive.org/details/zenodo).
- Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich. *Hegels Science of Logic.* Prometheus Books, New York, USA, 1991. ISBN 13: 9781573922807.
- David Hilbert. Die grundlagen der physik. *Nachrichten von der Gesellschaft der Wissenschaften zu Göttingen – Mathematisch-Physikalische Klasse*, 3:395–407, 1915.
- Theodor Kaluza. Zum unitätsproblem der physik. *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften* (Berlin, pages 966–972, 1921).
- Oskar Klein. The atomicity of electricity as a quantum theory law. *Nature*, 118(2971):516–516, 1926a.
- Oskar Klein. Quantentheorie und fünfdimensionale relativitätstheorie. *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 37(12):895–906, 1926b.
- Leopold Kronecker. Ueber bilineare Formen. *Journal für die reine und angewandte Mathematik (Crelle’s Journal)*, 68:273–285, 1868.
- Joseph Larmor. A dynamical theory of the electric and luminiferous medium, part iii. relations with material media. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical or Physical Character*, A195:1–77, 1900. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1900.0021.
- Max von Laue. Interferenzerscheinungen bei röntgenstrahlen. *Annalen der Physik*, 346(15):965–982, 1912.
- Hendrik Antoon Lorentz. La théorie électromagnétique de maxwell et son application aux corps mouvants. *Archives néerlandaises des sciences exactes et naturelles*, 14:669–714, 1909.
- James Clerk Maxwell. A dynamical theory of the electromagnetic field. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, 155:459–512, 1865. doi: 10.1098/rstl.1865.0008.
- Charles W. Misner, Kip S. Thorne, and John A. Wheeler. *Gravitation.* Freeman, 1973.
- Emmy Noether. Invariante variationsprobleme. *Nachrichten von der Gesellschaft der Wissenschaften zu Göttingen, Mathematisch-Physikalische Klasse*, 1918:235–257, 1918.
- Gregorio Ricci-Curbastro and Tullio Levi-Civita. Méthodes de calcul différentiel absolu et leurs applications. *Mathematische Annalen*, 54(1):125–201, 3 1900. ISSN 1432-1807. doi: 10.1007/BF01454201.
- Hans Stephani, editor. *Exact solutions of Einstein’s field equations.* Cambridge monographs on mathematical physics. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK ; New York, 2nd ed edition, 2003. ISBN 978-0-521-46136-8.
- John Venn. I. On the Diagrammatic and Mechanical Representation of Propositions and Reasonings. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 10(59):1–18, 1880. doi: 10.1080/14786448008626877. [Taylor and Francis](https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14786448008626877).
- John Venn. *Symbolic logic.* Macmillan and Co., 1881. [archive.org](https://www.archive.org/details/zenodo).
- Max von Laue. Zur Dynamik der Relativitätstheorie. *Annalen der Physik*, 340(8):524–542, 1911. ISSN 1521-3889. doi: 10.1002/andp.19113400808. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/andp.19113400808>.
- Max von Laue. Das relativitätsprinzip. *Physikalische Zeitschrift*, 19:49–52, 1918. doi: 10.1515/zp-1918-19-1-49.
- G. Vranceanu. Sur une théorie unitaire non holonome des champs physiques. *Journal de Physique et le Radium*, 7(12): 514–526, 1936. ISSN 0368-3842. doi: 10.1051/jphysrad:01936007012051400. URL <http://www.edpsciences.org/10.1051/jphysrad:01936007012051400>.
- Causation ISSN: 1863-9542 <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207574> Volume 20, Issue 3, 5–43

Hermann Weyl. Gravitation und elektrizität. Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 465:389–405, 1918.

G Zehfuss. Über eine gewisse Determinante. Zeitschrift für Mathematik und Physik, 3:298–301, 1858.

Fritz Zwicky. Die Rotverschiebung von extragalaktischen Nebeln. Helvetica physica acta, 6:110–127, 1933.

Блохинцев, Дмитрий Иванович and Гальперин, Ф. М. Гипотеза нейтрино и закон сохранения энергии. Под Знаменем Марксизма, 6:147–157, 1934.

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